

Nucleophilic Reactivity Constants in S_N2 Reactions

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Kinetics of reaction of benzylchloride, *p*-nitrobenzylchloride, methyl and ethyl iodides with fourteen nitrogen bases in nitrobenzene-ethanol mixtures have been studied. The results could be fitted into Swain-Scott, and Edward's relationship.

We have earlier reported the kinetics of methyl iodide-aniline¹ and ethyl iodide-aniline² in nitrobenzene medium and kinetics of benzylchloride-aniline in nitrobenzene-ethanol mixtures³. In the present communication an attempt is made for computation of nucleophilicity parameters.

EXPERIMENTAL

Nitrobenzene, aromatic amines, benzylchloride and *p*-nitrobenzylchloride were purified as described earlier. The boiling points at atmospheric pressure and refractive indices for the sodium line at 20° of the compounds were nitrobenzene 210°, nD 1.5524; aniline 183°, nD 1.5863; N-methylaniline 193°, nD 1.5702; dimethylaniline 193°, nD 1.5587; *p*-toluidine 45°*; *m*-toluidine 199°, nD 1.5711; *o*-toluidine 197°, nD 1.5728; *p*-chloroaniline 70°*; *m*-chloroaniline 230°, nD 1.5931; *o*-chloroaniline 207°, nD 1.5895; *m*-bromoaniline 251°, nD 1.6260; β -naphthylamine 111°*; benzylchloride 169°, nD 1.5391 and *p*-nitrobenzylchloride 71°*.

Methyl and ethyl iodides were of Riedel (pure) whereas aliphatic amines were of analar grade. Rate measurements were done as described earlier³.

DISCUSSION

Swain and Scott⁴ have shown $\log k/k_0 = S_n$ where 'S' is the susceptibility factor and 'n' is the nucleophilicity constant. From the literature 'S' value for benzylchloride (0.87) was chosen. This has been computed from aqueous data but Swain and Scott state that variation in 'S' is small with temperature and change in solvent. This approximation does not affect the computation of relative nucleophilicities of the various nucleophiles.

* = Melting points.

1. P. S. R. Murti and G. P. Panigrahi, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 430, 5.
2. P. S. R. Murti and G. P. Panigrahi, Communicated to *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*
3. P. S. R. Murti and G. P. Panigrahi, *Israel J. Chem.*, 1968, **6**, 2.
4. C. G. Swain and C. B. Scott, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 141.

Data are summarized in the following table.

TABLE I

Comparison of nucleophilicity constant with second order rate constants ($\times 10^3$ l. moles⁻¹ min⁻¹) at 80° for reactions of nucleophiles with methyl iodide, ethyl iodide, benzyl chloride, and *p*-nitrobenzyl chloride.

Nucleophile	(log k_0 for benzyl chloride = .7929, 'S' for benzyl chloride = 0.87)				
	Nucleophilicity constant 'n'	k^* (CH ₃ I)	k (C ₂ H ₅ I)	k (C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ Cl)	k (<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ Cl)
Aniline	4.5	55.37	8.00†	7.55	3.56
N-methylaniline	4.9	141.90	13.43	16.63	6.16
β -naphthylamine	4.4	54.29	—	6.61	2.33
<i>p</i> -toluidine	4.8	155.60	19.90†	14.92	11.61
<i>m</i> -toluidine	4.7	97.00	10.41	10.96	4.98
<i>o</i> -toluidine	4.3	30.68	4.46	4.67	2.86
<i>p</i> -chloroaniline	4.1	18.50	3.32	3.72	1.49
<i>m</i> -chloroaniline	3.9	8.70	1.40	2.43	0.85
<i>m</i> -bromoaniline	4.2	10.90	—	3.45	1.69
Pyridine	4.8	—	—	14.44	6.37
Dimethylamine	6.9	—	—	879.6	517.45
Diethylamine	6.0	—	—	147.7	75.72
<i>n</i> -butylamine	5.8	—	—	112.6	83.43
Benzylamine	5.5	—	—	62.84	42.04

Note:—Pure nitrobenzene has been used as the solvent in the reactions with methyl and ethyl iodides whereas nitrobenzene-ethanol (80 : 20 v/v) was used as solvent in reactions with benzyl chloride and *p*-nitrobenzyl chloride).

* Values are for the first step of the primary amines computed by Frost-Schwemer treatment^{5,6}.

† Values are for the first step computed by Frost-Schwemer treatment.

(log K_0 for benzyl chloride = 9.9729, 'S' for benzyl chloride = 0.87)

It is also observed that the pK_a values of the above nucleophiles were found to be linear to the computed nucleophilicity constants.

The accuracy or otherwise of the computation was checked by using these values in other reactions where conditions are different but the reaction mechanism is same established by linear plots when logarithms of rate constants, for those nucleophiles with different substrates, are plotted. Such being the case it is found that a plot of log k (methyl iodide-bases)

5. A. A. Frost, and W. C. Schwemer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 4541.

6. A. A. Frost and W. C. Schwemer, *ibid*, 1952, **74**, 1268.

Vs ' n ', $\log k$ (ethyl iodide-bases) Vs ' n ' and $\log k$ (*p*-nitrobenzylchloride—bases) Vs ' n ' yielded excellent plots. (Figs. 1, 2 and 3).

This itself is an indication that the values are fairly accurate. It is postulated that as long as the mechanism is the same an alteration in environment or temperature does not substantially affect the correlation of ' n ' with $\log k$. When the mechanisms are different it is evident that though the nucleophiles are the same, ' n ' values will be different as seen in the work of Pearson⁷.

The method discussed⁸ was adopted for the computation of ' S ' value of CH_3I , $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{I}$ and *p*-nitrobenzylchloride. Plots of $\log k$ Vs ' n ' yielded slopes of 1.3, 1.1 and 0.9 respectively. It is interesting to note that the ' S ' value of CH_3I reported by Pearson (loc.cit.) is 1.4 as compared to 1.3 computed by us. This is enough evidence of the applicability of the equation for these systems.

Swin-Scott linear free energy relationship has been improved upon by Edwards⁹ by a four parameter equation. It has been noted that the electrode potentials, for many reactions, parallel the nucleophilicity of many ions.

$$\text{Edwards' postulate is } \log k/k_0 = \alpha E_n + \beta H.$$

7. R. G. Pearson, H. Sobel and J. Songstad, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 319.

8. E. S. Amis, 'Solvent effects on Reaction rates and mechanisms', Academic Press, New York, 1966. p. 169,

9. J. O. Edwards, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 1540.

where ' α ' and ' β ' are the constants of the substrate. The other parameters are defined as follows

$$E_n = E^0 + 2.6$$

$$H = pK_\alpha + 1.74$$

Using the kinetic data, H value and α and β of benzylchloride from literature ' E_n ', values are computed. They are tabulated below for the various nucleophiles.

TABLE II

$$\alpha \text{ (for Benzylchloride)} = 3.53$$

$$\beta \text{ (for Benzylchloride)} = -0.128$$

<i>Nucleophiles</i>	<i>H</i>	<i>E_n</i>
Aniline	5.99	1.32
β -Naphthylamine	5.85	1.30
N-Methylaniline	6.59	1.44
<i>p</i> -Toluidine	6.81	1.44
<i>m</i> -Toluidine	6.41	1.39
<i>o</i> -Toluidine	6.12	1.27
<i>p</i> -Chloroaniline	5.55	1.22
<i>m</i> -Chloroaniline	5.06	1.15
<i>m</i> -Bromoaniline	5.25	1.2
Pyridine	6.91	1.44
Dimethylamine	12.45	2.14
Diethylamine	12.84	1.94
<i>n</i> -Butylamine	12.35	1.89
Benzylamine	11.08	1.77

The accuracy of the E_n values was also checked by plotting $\log k$ of reactions involving methyl iodide-amines, ethyl iodide-amines and *p*-nitrobenzylchloride-amines Vs E_n values. All the plots were perfectly linear indicating the general applicability of the E_n values in reactions of the same mechanistic pathway.

It is comforting that ' n ' values and ' E_n ' values bear a linear relationship as seen by the plot (Fig. 4). Such correlation has been made by Pearson before. For the other substrates namely, CH_3I , $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{I}$ and *p*-nitrobenzylchloride α , β are not available. They have been computed by using the partial and multiple correlation theory¹⁰.

In our present case

$$\log k/k_0 = \alpha E_n + \beta H \quad (1)$$

10. C. H. Goulden, 'Methods of Statistical Analysis', 2nd Edition, Chapter VII and VIII, John Wiley and Sons, New York, 1959.

where we estimate the values of α and β , from the data. Naturally, we would like to determine them on the principle of least square. But since, here we find that E_n and H are independent, we can avail the convenience of obtaining them as gradient of line of best fit of $\log k/k_0$ over E_n and H respectively.

This is what we have availed of. We have determined β , as the gradient of line of best fit of $\log k/k_0$ over H , of course graphically, for reasons of simplicity and convenience.

Then, for obtaining α , we determine α from equation (1), by averaging all α 's, obtained in each case. This process has been adopted to verify β , which has been obtained by fitting a line of best visually. If all α 's come out to be nearly equal, β determined from the line is adoptable.

TABLE III

<i>Substrate</i>	α	β
CH ₃ I	4.5	0.075
C ₂ H ₅ I	3.5	0.0675
<i>p</i> -nitrobenzylchloride	2.752	0.02348

These equations, though empirical, do help in correlating to some extent structure and reactivity.

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